

How to Develop Key Stakeholders Trust in Terms of Corporate Reputation

Migle Matuleviciene, Jurgita Stravinskiene

Kaunas University of Technology

K. Donelaicio st. 73, 44029, Kaunas, Lithuania

E-mail. migle.matuleviciene@gmail.com, jurgita.stravinskiene@ktu.lt

crossref <http://dx.doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.27.4.13987>

In scientific literature, the trust of key stakeholders is considered to be the base for the survival of organizations. In the context of the relation between corporate reputation and the trust of stakeholders, scientists agree on evident importance of corporate reputation for the development of stakeholder trust in the organization; however, there is a lack of recommendations suggesting how an organization should develop the trust of key stakeholders using corporate reputation. The article presents a summarized view on the relationship between the main dimensions of corporate reputation and the factors of key stakeholder trust in the organization. Such relationships reveal that it is purposeful to invoke corporate reputation in order to develop trust of key stakeholders. Also, the article states the relation between the factors determining different stakeholders' trust in the organization and different dimensions of corporate reputation based on which the trust of the key stakeholders of the organization should be developed. The result of the theoretical study is a developed conceptual model of key stakeholder trust development in terms of corporate reputation. The model will be applied in further empirical studies on the development of trust of the key stakeholders: customers, employees, shareholders and suppliers.

Keywords: Trust, Development of Trust, Corporate Reputation, Key Stakeholders, Organization.

Introduction

Analysis of the scientific literature on the development of trust of key stakeholders in an organization revealed that the development of trust of key stakeholders in an organization is analyzed within two contexts: building of trust and restoration of trust. These views caused a necessity to analyse how organizations should develop the trust of the key stakeholders in terms of corporate reputation in order to ensure not only successful everyday activities of the organization but also the survival of the organization in case of critical situations. Therefore, further analysis of corporate reputation, in consideration of its importance to stakeholder trust, is necessary.

The *research problem* is structured as a question, i.e. how to develop the trust of the key stakeholders in terms of corporate reputation?

The *research aims* to reveal the development process of key stakeholders trust in terms of corporate reputation

The *object of this research* is the revelation of the development of the key stakeholder trust in terms of corporate reputation.

The *research methods* involve systemic and comparative analysis of scientific literature.

Literature Review

Identification and Argumentation of Key Stakeholders of an Organization

Scientists, in order to distance themselves from the identification of particular stakeholders of an organization, use stakeholder classification according to particular criteria, thus it is not known which stakeholders may be considered to be major. Despite of that, classification of stakeholders into homogenous groups (Fiedler &

Kirchgeorg, 2007) is a strong basis for identification of key stakeholders.

The main criterion of stakeholder classification is stakeholder influence on/power over the organizational activities (Bryson, 2004; Florea & Florea, 2013; Freeman, 1984; Gil-Lafuente & Paula, 2013; Gregory, 2007; Henriques & Sadorsky, 1999; Mitchell *et al.*, 1997; Polonsky & Scott, 2005); some scientists name this as organization's dependence on the stakeholders and closeness of the stakeholders to the organization (Gil-Lafuente & Paula, 2013). According to Gil-Lafuente and Paula (2013), the closest stakeholders are those with whom the organization interacts most often or maintains long-term relationships and that influence daily activities of the organization. On the basis of this approach, customers, employees, shareholders and suppliers were considered as the key stakeholders of an organization.

Development of Key Stakeholders Trust in Terms of Corporate Reputation

Weber *et al.* (2015) define the development of trust as "the process by which that state is achieved, shaped, and influenced" (p. 78). Many other scientists, including Dietz and Hartog (2006), Doney and Cannon (1997), Fang *et al.* (2008), Laeequddin *et al.* (2012), Schilke and Cook (2013), Six and Skinner (2010) also treat the development of trust as the process. After analyzing the development of key stakeholders trust in terms of corporate reputation the following statements can be made:

1. There are stages in trust development.
2. Corporate reputation may be considered as the main factor of trust development.
3. The trust can be of cognitive and emotional nature.
4. Trust in the representatives of the organization may be related to trust in the organization itself.

According to Bennett and Gabriel (2001), Dowling (2004), Iannuzzi (2000), Jahansoozi (2006), Park *et al.* (2012¹), Schanz (2009), the research data of “Edelman Trust Barometer” (2014), the research data of “Reputation Institute” (2012), Van der Merwe (2014), Verhoeven *et al.* (2012) it can be stated that corporate reputation can create or develop the stakeholder trust while introducing, attracting and encouraging stakeholders to approach, commit, cooperate with the organization, adopt to invest; it can also reduce the risk of stakeholder withdrawal. Based on this, a conclusion is made that corporate reputation can be considered as a very important factor while aiming to develop the trust of the stakeholders in the organization. This forces to perform a more detailed analysis on how corporate reputation relates to trust of particular stakeholders.

Fundamental dimensions of corporate reputation. The scientific literature provides many dimensions of corporate reputation that can be combined, grouped and compared considering their relation to certain stakeholders. Time-tested reputation assessment methodologies “Fortune 500”, “Reputation Quotient”, and “RepTrak” are based on similar corporate reputation dimensions that are analogous to the

dimensions identified by Fombrun and van Riel in 1999 and that most of the scientists have been using for many years. These dimensions are emotional appeal, products and services, financial performance, vision and leadership, workplace environment, and social responsibility.

Eisenegger (2009) provides a more common approach on corporate reputation dimensions. According to Eisenegger (2009), reputation is comprised of three basic dimensions - characteristics to all persons and organizations - that help to perceive the general reputation; these are functional, social and expressive dimensions. The functional dimension is based on rationality and expresses objective truth about the organization through the competences and successful activities of the organization. The social dimension is based on ethical organization performance, expresses social benevolence of the organization through fairness and responsibility of the organization. The expressive dimension is based on subjective beauty of the organization. It was noticed that these corporate reputation dimensions suggested by Eisenegger (2009) properly define and combine the main dimensions of corporate reputation found in the scientific literature (see Table 1).

Table 1

Structure of Corporate Reputation (Based on Eisenegger, 2009)

Object	Dimensions	Subdimensions		
CORPORATE REPUTATION	FUNCTIONAL	Financial performance	Good financial results Global reach	
		Vision and leadership	Quality of management Business strategy Organisation structure Leadership	
			Products and services	Product offer Customer orientation Innovation and value creation
				SOCIAL
		Social responsibility		
			EXPRESSIVE	

Factors affecting major stakeholders trust. The scientists differently view and identify the factors of stakeholder trust in the organization. In the reviewed scientific literature, no uniform approach is found to what factors determine stakeholder trust in the organization. After

a detailed analysis of the scientific literature, the factors of the key stakeholders - customers, employees, shareholders, and suppliers - trust in the organization were identified (see Table 2).

Table 2

Factors Affecting Key Stakeholders Trust

Stakeholder	Factors affecting stakeholders trust	Source
Customers	- quality of products and services - good organization (as an employer) status - customer orientation - social and environmental responsibility - financial stability of the organization	Boshoff (2009), Shahsavari and Faryabi (2013), Terblanche (2014), Walsh and Beatty (2007), Walsh <i>et al.</i> (2009 ¹ , 2009 ²)
Employees	- leadership - employee involvement in the management of the organization - human resource management	Gould-Williams (2003), Lau and Liden (2008), Sendjaya and Pekerti (2010), Xu and Thomas (2011)
Shareholders	- corporate management (with reference to corporate governance ratings)	Ertugrul and Hegde (2009), Klozikova and Dockalikova (2014), Shank <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Suppliers	- product - business - personalities - relationship - third parties	Viitaharju and Lahdesmaki (2012)

The relationship between the main dimensions of corporate reputation and the factors of key stakeholder trust in the organization. After identification of the main dimensions of corporate reputation found in the scientific literature, it was observed that these dimensions are related

- and quite often even identical - to factors of key stakeholder trust in the organization provided by the scientists. In other words, corporate reputation dimensions reveal that the trust of stakeholders can be based on certain corporate reputation dimensions (see Table 3).

Table 3

Interpretation of the Relationship between the Factors Determining the Stakeholders Trust in the Organization and the Equated Corporate Reputation Dimensions (Developed on the Basis of Theoretical Studies on Stakeholders Trust in an Organization and Corporate Reputation)

Stakeholder	Factors affecting stakeholders trust in the organization	The dimensions of corporate reputation equated to factors affecting stakeholders trust in the organization
Customers	Quality of products and services	Products and services
	Good organization (as an employer) status	Workplace environment
		Human resources
	Customer orientation	Customer orientation
	Social and environmental responsibility	Social responsibility
		Fair, ethical organization performance
		Human resources
Financial stability of the organization	Good financial results	
	Global reach	
	Vision and leadership	
	Innovation and value creation	
Employees	Leadership	Vision and leadership
	Employee involvement in the management of the organization	Workplace environment
		Organizational culture
		Human resources
	Human resource management	Human resources
		Workplace environment
		Social responsibility
Fair, ethical organization performance		
Shareholders	Corporate management (with reference to corporate governance ratings)	Good financial results
		Global reach
		Quality of management
		Business strategy
		Organization structure
		Leadership
		Suppliers
Business	Brand image	
	Customer orientation	
	Good financial results	
	Global reach	
Personalities	Business strategy	
Relationship	Human resources	
	Organizational culture	
Third parties	Emotional attractiveness	
		Fair, ethical organization performance
		Positive media image

The relationship between the factors determining the stakeholder trust in the organization and the dimensions of corporate reputation revealed the purposefulness of invoking corporate reputation in order to develop stakeholder trust. It is concluded that factors of different stakeholders' trust in the organization are related to different corporate reputation dimensions.

Results

Based on the discussed theoretical studies on key stakeholders of an organization, stakeholder trust development, corporate reputation, and the factors determining the stakeholder trust, a conceptual model of key stakeholder trust development concerning the aspect of corporate reputation has been developed (see Figure 1).

The conceptual model of key stakeholder trust development in terms of corporate reputation reflects

stakeholder trust development of dual nature: trust between the stakeholder as a person and the organization (trust developed in three stages) and trust between the stakeholder as an organization and the organization (interorganizational trust developed in four stages).

In the first stage, the stakeholder (i.e. a person or a person representing an organization) starts collecting information on trustworthiness of another organization. As it has been already revealed by earlier theoretical studies, corporate reputation is considered to be a reliable source of information about the organization. In the second stage, the person or the person representing the stakeholder investigates, checks and evaluates the collected information. In case the information (cognitive) collected by the person meets a personal perception of the organization's trustworthiness, the interaction progresses to the third stage - formation of cognitive personal trust by the stakeholder as a person.

construction and real estate companies, food and beverage manufacturers, pharmaceutical companies, banks and insurance companies, transport and transport companies, telecommunication companies and information technology companies. It should be noted that the majority of listed business sectors have faced crises which have negatively affected the reputation of the aforementioned business sectors. One of more interesting but less obvious remarks is that distrust in one business sector can reduce the trust in other similar business sector. In the media, pharmaceutical

sector is often identified with pharmacy sector. This situation increases public distrust of pharmacies. Invoking appropriate dimensions of corporate reputation it is possible to reduce the impact of third parties on stakeholder trust in particular business sector by developing stakeholder trust. Considering the problem of identifying pharmaceutical sector with pharmacy sector it can be useful to verify empirically the development of key stakeholders trust in case of pharmacy sector.

References

- Bennett, R., & Gabriel, H. (2001). Reputation, trust and supplier commitment: the case of shipping company/seaport relations. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 16 (6), 424–438. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/EUM000000006018>
- Boshoff, C. (2009). A psychometric assessment of an instrument to measure a service firm's customer-based corporate reputation. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 40 (2), 35–44.
- Bryson, J. M. (2004). What to do when stakeholders matter. Stakeholder identification and analysis techniques. *Public Management Review*, 6 (1), 21–53. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14719030410001675722>
- Dietz, G., & Hartog, D. N. D. (2006). Measuring trust inside organisations. *Personnel Review*, 35 (5), 557–588. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00483480610682299>
- Doney, P. M., & Cannon, J. P. (1997). An examination of the nature of trust in buyer-seller relationships. *Journal of Marketing*, 61, 35–51. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1251829>
- Dowling, G. R. (2004). Corporate reputations: should you compete on yours? *California Management Review*, 46 (3), 19–36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/41166219>
- Edelman. (2014). 2014 Edelman Trust Barometer. Building Trust. Available from internet: <http://www.edelman.com/insights/intellectual-property/2014-edelman-trust-barometer/building-trust/>
- Eisenegger, M. (2009). Trust and reputation in the age of globalisation. In: J. Klewes, & R. Wreschniok (Eds.), *Reputation capital. Building and maintaining trust in the 21st century* (pp.11–22). Berlin: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-01630-1_2
- Ertugrul, M., & Hegde, S. (2009). Corporate governance ratings and firm performance. *Financial Management, Spring*, 139–160. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-053X.2009.01031.x>
- Fang, E., Palmatier, R. W., Scheer, L. K., & Li, N. (2008). Trust at different organizational levels. *Journal of Marketing*, 72, 80–98. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.72.2.80>
- Fiedler, L., & Kirchgeorg, M. (2007). The role concept in corporate branding and stakeholder management reconsidered: are stakeholder groups really different? *Corporate Reputation Review*, 10 (3), 177–188. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.crr.1550050>
- Florea, R., & Florea, R. (2013). Stakeholders interests analyse and harmonization - starting point of strategic approach. *Economy Transdisciplinarity Cognition*, 16 (1), 130–135.
- Fortune 500. (2015). World's Most Admired Companies 2015. Nine Key Attributes of Reputation. Available from internet: <http://fortune.com/worlds-most-admired-companies/>
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: a stakeholder approach*. Boston: Pitman.
- Gil – Lafuente, A. M., & Paula, L. B. (2013). Algorithm applied in the identification of stakeholders. *Kybernetes*, 42 (5), 674–685. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/K-04-2013-0073>
- Gould-Williams, J. (2003). The importance of HR practices and workplace trust in achieving superior performance: a study of public-sector organizations. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14 (1), 28–54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09585190210158501>
- Gregory, A. (2007). Involving stakeholders in developing brands: the communication dimension. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 23 (1/2), 59–73. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1362/026725707X178558>
- Harris Interactive. (2015). The Harris Poll Reputation Quotient® (RQ®). Available from internet: <http://www.harrisinteractive.com/Products/ReputationQuotient.aspx>
- Henriques, I., & Sadorsky, P. (1999). The relationship between environmental commitment and managerial perceptions of stakeholder importance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 42 (1), 87–99. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/256876>

- Iannuzzi, A. (2000). Stakeholder trust: how do I get it? *Environmental Quality Management, Autumn*, 69–73. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1520-6483\(200023\)10:1<69::AID-TQEM8>3.0.CO;2-D](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1520-6483(200023)10:1<69::AID-TQEM8>3.0.CO;2-D)
- Jahansoozi, J. (2006). Organization – stakeholder relationships: exploring trust and transparency. *Journal of Management Development*, 25 (10), 942–955. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02621710610708577>
- Klozikova, J., & Dockalikova, I. (2014). Corporate governance rating: synthesis of rating models of corporate governance with utilization methods AHP and DEMATEL. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Management, Leadership & Governance*, 460–471.
- Laequddin, M., & Sardana, G. D. (2010). What breaks trust in customer supplier relationship? *Management Decision*, 48 (3), 353–365. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00251741011037738>
- Laequddin, M., Sahay, B. S., Sahay, V., & Waheed, K. A. (2012). Trust building in supply chain partners relationship: an integrated conceptual model. *Journal of Management Development*, 31 (6), 550–564. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02621711211230858>
- Lau, D. C., & Liden, R. C. (2008). Antecedents of coworker trust: leaders' blessings. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93 (5), 1130–1138. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.93.5.1130>
- Mitchell, R. K., Agle, B. R., & Wood, D. J. (1997). Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: defining the principle of who and what really counts. *Academy of Management Review*, 22 (4), 853–886.
- Nova Media", public relations company (2013). Pasitikėjimas verslu Lietuvoje. Available from internet: http://www.novamedia.lt/tyrimai/Tyrimo%20ataskaita_2013_atnaujinta.pdf
- Park, J., Gunn, F., & Han, S. L. (2012). Multidimensional trust building in e-retailing: cross-cultural differences in trust formation and implications for perceived risk. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 19, 304–312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2012.03.003>
- Polonsky, M. J., & Scott, D. (2005). An empirical examination of the stakeholder strategy matrix. *European Journal of Marketing*, 39 (9/10), 1199–1215. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/03090560510610806>
- Reputation Institute. (2012). The 2012 Global RepTrak® 100: results and report. Available from internet: http://www.rankingthebrands.com/PDF/2012%20RepTrak%20100-Global_Report,%20Reputation%20Institute.pdf
- Schanz, K. U. (2009). Maintaining stakeholder trust in difficult times: some fundamental reflections in light of the credit crisis. *The Geneva Papers*, 34, 260–270. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/gpp.2009.4>
- Schilke, O., & Cook, K. S. (2013). A cross-level process theory of trust development in interorganizational relationships. *Strategic Organization*, 11 (3), 281–303. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1476127012472096>
- Sendjaya, S., & Pekerti, A. (2010). Servant leadership as antecedent of trust in organizations. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 31 (7), 643–663. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437731011079673>
- Shahsavari, A., & Faryabi, M. (2013). The effect of customer-based corporate reputation on customers' citizenship behaviors in banking industry. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 6 (20), 3746–3755.
- Shank, T., Hill, R. P., & Stang, J. (2013). Do investors benefit from good corporate governance? *Corporate Governance*, 13 (4), 384–396. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/CG-03-2010-0027>
- Six, F., & Skinner, D. (2010). Managing trust and trouble in interpersonal work relationships: evidence from two Dutch organizations. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21 (1), 109–124. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09585190903466913>
- Terblanche, N. S. (2014). Validation of the customer-based corporate reputation scale in a retail context. *International Journal of Market Research*, 56 (5), 655–671. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2501/IJMR-2014-044>
- Van der Merwe, W. A. J., & Puth, G. (2014). Towards a conceptual model of the relationship between corporate trust and corporate reputation. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 17, 138–156. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/crr.2014.4>
- Verhoeven, J. W. M., Van Hoof, J. J., Keurs, V. T., & Van Vuuren, M. (2012). Effects of apologies and crisis responsibility on corporate and spokesperson reputation. *Public Relations Review*, 38, 501–504. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2012.02.002>
- Viitaharju, L., & Lahdesmaki, M. (2012). Antecedents of trust in asymmetrical business relationships. Differing perceptions between food producers and retailers. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 30 (5), 567–587. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02634501211251061>
- Walsh, G., & Beatty, S. E. (2007). Customer-based corporate reputation of a service firm: scale development and validation. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 35, 127–143. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11747-007-0015-7>

- Walsh, G., Beatty, S. E., & Shiu, E. M. K. (20091). The customer-based corporate reputation scale: replication and short form. *Journal of Business Research*, 62, 924–930.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2007.11.018>
- Walsh, G., Mitchell, V. W., Jackson, P. R., & Beatty, S. E. (20092). Examining the antecedents and consequences of corporate reputation: a customer perspective. *British Journal of Management*, 20, 187–203.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8551.2007.00557.x>
- Weber, J. M., Malhotra, D., & Murnighan, J. K. (2005). Normal acts of irrational trust: motivated attributions and the trust development process. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 26, 75–101.[http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0191-3085\(04\)26003-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0191-3085(04)26003-8)
- Xu, J., & Thomas, H. C. (2011). How can leaders achieve high employee engagement? *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 32 (4), 399–416.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437731111134661>

The article has been reviewed.

Received in January, 2016; accepted in October, 2016.